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DICHIARAZIONE DI BERLINO

PER UN MODELLO UMANO DELLE POLITICHE SULLE DROGHE.

La guerra alla droga ha generato una spirale di violenza sempre più distruttiva.

I principi che sono alla base del proibizionismo hanno fallito totalmente il loro intento. Il tentativo di un mondo senza droghe attraverso la riduzione dell'offerta e la repressione sui consumatori mediante la violenza di stato non è in accordo con la realtà dei popoli e degli stati, poiché fomenta strutture antidemocratiche, repressive e autoritarie che rafforzano l'influenza economica del crimine organizzato.

La guerra globale contro le droghe porta a violazioni sistematiche dei diritti umani, corruzione, aumento incontrollato dei detenuti e dei procedimenti giudiziari, aldilà di aumentare significativamente i rischi per la società civile e la salute dei consumatori di droghe illegali.

Il proibizionismo è un percorso politico sbagliato che si è trasformato in una guerra più o meno dichiarata in quanto la repressione delle droghe cresce in maniera smisurata nel triangolo a nord dell'America Centrale e nel Sud-Est Asiatico seminando terrore e morte.

Contemporaneamente, i successi ottenuti decriminalizzando e orientando la ricerca per fini scientifici e terapeutici per l'uso di droghe illegali in altre regioni del mondo, ha dimostrato ancor più l'elevata incongruenza del proibizionismo.

Ciò dimostra che gli sforzi della società civile e della comunità scientifica sulla materia stanno contribuendo a migliorare la qualità di vita dei consumatori di droghe, permettendo di combattere le dipendenze attraverso l'accesso a basilari servizi sociali e di salute formati sulla metodologia della riduzione del danno.

Per questo, in risposta alle sofferenze di milioni di persone che soffrono le conseguenze della guerra alla droga, noi come uomini e donne di diversa visione del mondo, cristiani, attivisti e liberi pensatori; difensori dei diritti umani e dei diritti dei di chi consuma droghe, rivolgiamo questa esortazione alle Nazioni Unite, all'ufficio delle Nazioni Unite per la droga e la delinquenza, alla commissione sui narcotici e le droghe, all'Unione Europea, CICAD, OAS, CELAC, ai politici chiese, comunità ed organizzazioni sociali: PONETE FINE ALLA GUERRA CONTRO LA DROGA.

Sulla base del "Processo di riconciliazione, pace, giustizia e creazione" facciamo appello alle organizzazioni di base, alla comunità cristiana, alle associazioni laiche, civili, agli organismi internazionali, nel perseguire attivamente la fine della guerra alle droghe.

Esortiamo per un necessario approfondimento della cooperazione giudiziaria al fine di tracciare strategie reali di contrasto al crimine organizzato e al riciclaggio di denaro e di beni.

Nella promozione ed analisi obiettiva di alternative valide alle politiche basate sul proibizionismo e la repressione.

L'implementazione di strategie per la prevenzione dell'uso di droghe basata sull'educazione ai diritti umani e sui principi della riduzione del danno.

Promuovere una maggior partecipazione e impegno della società civile nel processo post UNGASS.

Il finanziamento di campagne internazionali che includano formazione sulle politiche sulla droga internazionali e locali, formazione per la prevenzione ed educazione attraverso dati scientifici validi e genuini, privi dei preconcetti e mistificazioni sui consumatori e sulle proprietà delle sostanze.

Che si riconosca la privacy degli assuntori di droga e la libertà per gli stessi di decidere la propria condotta di vita e la propria autodeterminazione.

In calce sono presenti le istituzioni e i leader firmatari di questa dichiarazione.

Ci impegnamo nel promuovere una riforma dell'attuale modello di controllo internazionale delle droghe basata sugli aspetti socio-sanitari e dei diritti umani.

Questa riforma deve individuare delle strategie compensative alle conseguenze negative delle politiche attuali, prevenire gli abusi di tutti i tipi di sostanze psicoattive ed alcoliche e combattere il traffico di droga.

Uniti nella diversità, in armonia con la giustizia e l'amore che ci muove siamo fermi nell'affermare che: LA GUERRA CONTRO LA DROGA DEVE CESSARE.

Initiators

Rev. Martin Diaz

International Consulting. Drug Policy and Harm Reduction Advocacy. President of IEPES

Theol. Daniela Kreher

Researcher, Pastoral With Youth, Harm Reduction, Drug Policy Advocacy. IEPES

Pfr. Michael Kleim

Theologian and activist for human rights. Member of the Schildower Kreis network of experts in science and practice. Germany

Religious Leaders

Padre José Alejandro Solalinde

Theologian and Catholic Priest, defender of the human rights of migrants. Coordinator of the Pastoral of Human Mobility South Pacific of the Mexican Episcopate.

Padre Luis Barrios

Theologian and Professor of John Jay College of Criminal Justice & Member of Ph.D. faculties in critical social/personality psychology. Graduate Center-City University of New York; Fellow American College of Forensic Examiner Institute-FECEI

Rvdo. Martín Barahona

Bishop Emeritus and Peace Ambassador of the Anglican Episcopal Church of El Salvador.

Dr. Dr. David A. Roldán

Dr. in Theology and Dr. in Philosophy, Dean of the Theological Institute FIET. Argentina

Lesley Murdock

Administrator | Multicultural Growth & Witness of Unitarian Universalist Association, USA

Rvdo. Miguel A. Hernandez

Priest in charge of Holy Trinity Episcopal Church in West Orange, NJ. USA

Rev. Graham Long AM

CEO/Pastor The Wayside Chapel, Australia

Rev. Margarita Sánchez

Bishop of Metropolitan Community Church (MCC), Dean of the MCC Garner Institute, Brazil.

Rev. Cristiano Valerio

Coordinator of MCC in the Southern Cone.

Rev. Héctor Gutiérrez

Elder of MCC – Metropolitan Christian Church. Associate Director of the Office of Emerging Ministries, Mexico

Fray Julián Cruzalta

Theologian and Activist for Human Rights, Mexico

Rev. Daniel Santos Rodríguez

Holder of the "Apostolic House Christ Libertador" Community of the City of Monterrey, Nuevo León, Mexico.

Rvdo. Mario Luna

Theologian, Ecumenical Church, El Salvador

Christoph Schmidt

Social Deacon, Germany

Ulrich Töpfer

Bund Evangelischer Jugend Mitteldeutschland, Deutschland

Academics and Experts

Noam Chomsky

Linguist, philosopher and activist. Professor Emeritus of Linguistics at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT). USA

David Nutt

DM FRCP FRCPsych FMedSci DLaws, Prof of Neuropsychopharmacology. Imperial College, UK

Dra. Raquel Peyraube

Consultant in Harm Reduction and Public Policies | Uruguay

Lic. Fidel Nieto

Rector of the Salvadorean Lutheran University, El Salvador

Lic. Dagoberto Gutiérrez

Vice-rector of the Salvadorean Lutheran University and Signer of the Peace Agreements, El Salvador

Dr. Sergio Sánchez Bustos

Medical Doctor and Director of "Latinoamérica Reforma" Foundation, Chile

Psic. Armando Loizaga Pazzi

Director of NIERIKA A.C. Multidisciplinary Association for the Preservation of Indigenous Traditions of Sacred Plants, Mexico

Dr. Mariano Fusero

Director of the Drug Policy Area of the Penal Thought Association (APP), Argentina.

Ernesto Cortés

Executive Director of the Costa Rican Association for the Study and Intervention in Drugs (ACEID), Costa Rica

Rodrigo Uprimny Yepes

Founder and Member of the Board of Directors of "Dejusticia", Colombia

Profesor Hakim Himmich

President of the Association for the Fight against AIDS (ALCS), Morocco

M.A. Natalia Navas

Bachelor of Science in Industrial and Labor Relations from Cornell University, Master of International Studies, CUNY Graduate Center (Postgraduate Center, University of New York City). Specialist in the sociological exploration of the patterns of globalized labor migration reflected in the new economy after the collapse of 2008. Militant for the rights of Migrants. USA

MSc. Astrid Hahner

Biology (Neurosciences) with expertise in psychedelic plant healing Berlin

Hans Cousto

Mathematician and musicologist. Expert in drugs. Author. Switzerland / Germany.

Dra. Rahel Gall

Director of CONTACT, Foundations of Addiction Assistance, Switzerland.

Jean-Félix Savary

Secretary General GREA – Groupement Romand d'Etudes des Addictions, Suiza

Dr. Milton Flores

Medical Psychiatrist, "Triagram" Institute for the Development of Life in Community, Chile

Dr. Alex Wodak AM

Emeritus Consultant, Alcohol and Drug Service, St Vincent's Hospital

Joycelyn Woods

Director National Alliance for Medication Assisted Recovery, N.Y. EEUU

Prof. Carla Rossi | Italia

Professor of Medical Statistics, Representative of Nonviolent Radical Party Transnational Transparty (NRPTT) to UNODC, Official National Expert of HRDU indicator to EMCDDA, President of the Association Centro Studi Statistici e Sociali

Zach Walsh, PhD, RPsych
Associate Professor | Psychology | The University of British Columbia, Canada

Dr. Marcus Day DSc
Director of Caribbean Drug & Alcohol Research Institute, Saint Lucia [1]

Eberhard Schatz
Coordinator CORRELATION network, c/o Foundation De REGENBOOG GROEP, Holanda

Oscar Hugo Espin Garcia
St public mental health master degree at UNAM & member of ssdp México chapter

Juan Machín
Director of the Caritas Center for "Training for Drug Dependence Care and Associated Critical Situations" A.C., Mexico

Lynne Raskin
CEO of South Riverdale Community Health Centre, Canada

Dr. Matthias von Reusner
Medical Doctor, Nueva York, USA

Dirk Schaeffer
Board Member of Deutsche AIDS Hilfe

Silke Reichrath
Co-founder Brook Valley Research for Education in Nonviolence.

Hans Sinn
Co-founder Brook Valley Research for Education in Nonviolence.

Mariana Pinzon
Sciences of Religion, German Hemp Association, Cannafem, Germany

Marcel Schage
Political scientist, Germany.

Joana Canêdo
Advocacy and Policy Officer of Agência Piaget para o Desenvolvimento (APDES), Portugal

Ethan A Nadelmann
Founder of Drug Policy Alliance

Ralf Gerlach
Institute for the Furtherance of Qualitative Drug Research, Acceptance-Oriented Drug Work, and Rational Drug Policy, Münster, Germany.

Aram Barra
Master in Politics and Public Administration from New York University and University College London. He is currently an independent consultant on health, safety and human rights issues.

Politicians, Officials and Former Officials

Bodo Ramelow
Prime Minister of Thuringia, Germany

Lic. Milton Romani Gerner
Former General Secretary of the National Drug Board and Former Ambassador of Uruguay to the Organization of American States. Uruguay

Hubert Wimber
Former president of the Münster police. Board Member of LEAP, Germany

Dr. Herbert Wilfredo Barillas
Former Rector of National University of El Salvador, El Salvador

Volker Beck
Member of federal parliament. Alliance 90/the Green's, Germany.

Andreas Müller
Juvenile Judge, Author, Germany.

Tibor Harrach
Pharmacist and Green Party candidate for the Bundestag, Berlin

Holger Gundlach
Former Director of the Department of Drugs of the National Office of Criminal Police of Hamburg, Germany.

Journalists and opinion makers:

Emilio Ruchansky
Journalist and author of "A world with drugs alternative roads to prohibition", Argentina

Roger Liggerstorfer
Editorial "Nachtschatten", Switzerland

Social Leaders

Roberto Cañas
Signing of the Peace Agreements, professor and political analyst. El Salvador

Enrico Fletzer
President of the European Coalition for Just and Effective Drug Policies -ENCOD, Italy.

Joyce A. Rivera, ABD, MA
Founder and Executive Director "Harm Reduction Corner" of Santa Ana, NY, USA

Anton M Djajaprawira
Executive Director of Rumah Cemara. Indonesia

Anke van Dam
Executive Director AFEW International, Amsterdam, Netherlands

Rubem César Fernandes
Director of "Viva Rio", Brazil

Anna Quigley
City Wide, Independent Councillor on Dublin City Council, Gregory Group, Community activist, Ireland

Farid Ghehiouèche
Head of advocacy, FAAAT think & do tank

André Nilsen
Chair of Normal Norge

Amy Romanello
Charité Universitätsmedizin zu Berlin, líder del capítulo de SSDP Berlín

Roar Mikalsen,
President of AROD

Dan Bigg
Director of Chicago Recovery Alliance, USA

Donna May
MUMSDU (moms united and mandated to saving the lives of Drug Users), Canada

Gretchen Burns Bergman
New PATH (Parents for Addiction Treatment & Healing) and Moms United to End the War on Drugs, California, USA

Dr J. Carolyn Gomes
Executive Director, Caribbean Vulnerable Communities Coalition (CVC), Jamaica

Joel Simpson
Founding Co-Chairperson, Society Against Sexual Orientation Discrimination, Guyana

J.R. Neuberger, CMA
Member, Board of Directors, National Alliance for Medication Assisted Recovery. J.R. Neuberger, CMA. USA

Emma Guadalupe Rodríguez Romero
President of SSDP-Students for a Sensible Drug Policy, Mexico.

Héctor Joel Anaya Segura
Director of SSDP-Students for a Sensible Drug Policy, Mexico.

Mark A. Varca, J.D.
Chairman, Federal CURE, Florida

Rachel Beth Wissner
Outreach Associate, Family Law & Cannabis Alliance, Massachusetts

Christian Hui
Co-founder and Chair, Canadian Positive People Network, HIV+ and PWU/ID activist, Dennis Sobin, Director. Safe Streets Arts Foundation, Washington, DC

Howard Gough
Executive Chairman Jamaica Psychosocial Foundation (JPF)

Wiqas Ahmad
International Working Group Member of Initiative for Youth and Sustainable Development, Pakistan

Ulrich Töpfer
Federation of Evangelical Youth Central Germany, Germany.

Graham de Barra
Executive Director of Help Not Harm, Ireland

Florian Scheibein
Deputy Director of HELP NOT HARM, Ireland

Ana Maria Gazmuri
CEO, Fundación Daya, Chile

Business and philanthropic leaders

Louis Santiago
Director at CannaSense Total Wellness, EEUU

John McAfee
Computer security expert

Law and Justice

Jack A. Cole
Retired Lieutenant of New Jersey Police Department. Co-Founder of Law Enforcement Against Prohibition. Honorary Council Member of Students for Sensible Drug Policy

Ronald Hampton
Retired Police Officer of the Metropolitan Police Department of Washington, DC, former Executive Director of Blacks In Law Enforcement of America.

Greg Barns
Barrister and former National President of the Australian Lawyers Alliance

Activists

Diego Grooscors
Independent activist, Costa Rica

Crack Rodríguez
Artist, El Salvador

Ian McKnight from
Community Activist, Jamaica

Karsten Tögel – Lins
"Legal High Inhaltsstoffe", Germany

Sebastian Bassy
Pflegedienstleitung Caritas Sozialstation, Germany

Sarah Nied
Germany

Dennis Karaula
Hanf Initiative. Frankfurt, Germany

Dirk Grimm
Mindzone, München, Germany

Holger Mueller
Student, Germany

Nic Voelk
Germany

Hendrikje Buhl
Germany

Matthias Hein
Germany

Moritz Rukiek
Germany

Reinhard Lehmann
Germany

Niels Biedermann
Germany

Immanuel Ziefle
Germany

Pia Huber
Germany

Michael Tillmanns
Germany

Uwe Vedder
Germany

Mark Zankl
Germany

Max Lausmann
Germany

Marcel Falke
Germany

Michael Thomas Bauer
Germany

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Germany

Peter Schneider
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Frans Bronkhorst
Netherlands

Matthias Rudelt
Germany

Herbert Pahlitzsch
Germany

Matthias Ulbrich
Germany

Richard Neubert
Germany

Jörg Schönthaler
Germany

Ralf Heinrich
Germany

Daniel Reusse
Germany

Sonja Faber
Germany

Marc Wenk
Educador/ Erzieher, Germany

Oda Meubrink
Germany

Florian Kraft
Germany

Laif Weishaupt
Germany

Alexandra Tarragoni Maillard
Ginebra Suiza

Organizations

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